

Reanalysis of the EMEA Pan-European ME Patient Survey by Machine Learning, Bimodal Analysis, and Local Outlier Factor

Abstract

Raw data from the EMEA Pan-European ME Patient Survey were analysed by several methods, including local outlier factor (LOF), supervised and unsupervised Machine Learning (ML), and bimodal fit of age at first symptoms. A total of 9,596 ME/CFS patients were included.

Age at first symptoms among males with ME/CFS follows a bimodal gamma mixture distribution, with approximately 60% of subjects developing the disease at a mean age of 27 years (SD = 13) and 40% at a mean age of 43 years (SD = 8). Males who develop the disease earlier in their lives experience more sensitivity to sound/noise, dizziness, and sleep problems, but less pain. They show a higher level of severity.

Females report more comorbidities than males, they have more PEM, and are less likely to be stable. Females are also less likely to begin the disease after an infection, but more likely to indicate vaccination as the triggering event. Despite these differences, females are not more severe and more fatigued than males.

LOF analysis identified 480 outliers (5%) who show increased deterioration over time, are less likely to develop the disease after an infection, and have first symptoms at a younger age. Logistic regression and Naive Bayes models were built to identify housebound patients (AUC 84%), outliers (AUC 88%), and subjects who tend to deteriorate over time (AUC 76%).

The application of both LOF and Naive Bayes models trained on it shows promise for identifying atypical ME patients who are candidates for investigation of monogenic causes of this disabling condition.

Methods

Data source

The results of the 2021 survey promoted by the European ME Alliance (EMEA) were kindly shared with me by one of the authors, upon request, along with a copy of the form. Since the raw data were never made public by EMEA, I won't share them in this repository. I received a `.xlsx` file including the answers of 11,297 patients. A description of the survey and a detailed analysis of the results have been released by EMEA in April 2024 (Angelsen A et Schei T, 2024).

Data filtering and editing

The original raw data included 11,297 subjects and 272 variables. Individuals without a ME/CFS diagnosis were removed (1,484 subjects), then 69 subjects with no specified gender were filtered out. Then, 4 patients whose year of birth was after the year of first symptoms were removed. Two males indicated as trigger pregnancy/birth, but their illness started years after birth: they were removed. Of the remaining 9,738 subjects, two male patients reported endometriosis as a comorbidity, and their data were edited to remove the inconsistency. Missing data were present in 145 subjects, and they were removed. The subjects selected from the original data set are 9,593.

Age at diagnosis was calculated as the year of first symptoms minus the year of birth. Age was calculated as 2021 minus the year of birth. Three further cases collected by me were added to the raw data (folder Supplementary Cases), for a total of 9,596 ME/CFS patients. After editing and selecting the variables, I included 23 parameters for each subject. Below is the description of the variables of the present analysis.

Variable	Type	Values
gender_n	binary	male (1), female (2)
trigger_n	integer	infection (1), accident/injury/surgery (2), traumatic life event (3), vaccine (4), pregnancy/birth (5), none (6), other (7)

Variable	Type	Values
relatives_n	binary	first degree relatives with ME/CFS (1), no relatives with ME/CFS (0)
fatigue_n	ordinal	not at all (1), a little (2), moderately (3), a lot (4), very much (5), not relevant (6)
muscleorjointpain_n	ordinal	not at all (1), a little (2), moderately (3), a lot (4), very much (5), not relevant (6)
dizziness_n	ordinal	not at all (1), a little (2), moderately (3), a lot (4), very much (5), not relevant (6)
sleepproblems_n	ordinal	not at all (1), a little (2), moderately (3), a lot (4), very much (5), not relevant (6)
sensitivity_n	ordinal	not at all (1), a little (2), moderately (3), a lot (4), very much (5), not relevant (6)
pem_n	ordinal	not at all (1), a little (2), moderately (3), a lot (4), very much (5), not relevant (6)
course_n	ordinal	mostly stable, small fluctuations (1); major fluctuations (2); fluctuating initially, then mostly stable (3); fluctuating initially, then mostly improvement (4); fluctuating initially, then mostly deterioration (5); mainly improvement (6); mainly deterioration (7)
fibromyalgia_n	binary	yes (1), no (0)
Hashimotosthyroiditis_n	binary	yes (1), no (0)
interstitialcystitis_n	binary	yes (1), no (0)
siccasyndrome_n	binary	yes (1), no (0)
irritablebowelsyndrome_n	binary	yes (1), no (0)
migraine_n	binary	yes (1), no (0)
allergies_n	binary	yes (1), no (0)
endometriosis_n	binary	yes (1), no (0)
asthma_n	binary	yes (1), no (0)
multiplechemicalsensitivities_n	binary	yes (1), no (0)
severity_n	ordinal	completely recovered (1); better than mild (2); mild (~50% reduction) (3); moderate, mostly housebound (4); severe, mostly bedridden (5); very severe, totally bedridden, needs help (6)
age_ill	numeric	age at illness onset (year_ill – year_born)
age	numeric	age in years (2021 – year_born)
duration	numeric	disease duration in years (2021 – year_ill)

Table 1. Variables of the present study.

For the majority of the following analyses, I expanded variables `course_n` and `trigger_n` into several binary variables, as indicated in the following table.

Binary Variable	Original variable	Original values
improving_n	course_n	4, 6
deteriorating_n	course_n	5, 7
stable_n	course_n	1, 3
fluctuating_n	course_n	2
improving_n	course_n	4, 6
infection_n	trigger_n	1
AIS_n	trigger_n	2
trauma_n	trigger_n	3
vaccine_n	trigger_n	4
pregnancy_n	trigger_n	5
no_trigger_n	trigger_n	6
other_n	trigger_n	7

Bimodal analysis of age at onset

The distributions of `age_ill` for females, males, and both sexes were analysed by maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) performed by the function `mixfit()` of the R package `mixR` (You Y, 2021). I asked for a bimodal density using normal, gamma, and lognormal densities. Then, I tested the fit by the two-sided Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (Marsaglia G et al. 2003), using the function `ks.test()` of the package `stats`. This method tests the following null hypothesis: the distribution comes from the fitted density. Therefore, a high p-value supports the fit.

Local outlier factor

I searched for outliers among patients by using the local outlier factor (LOF) algorithm (Breunig MM, 2000). I set 10 as the minimum value for `minPts` (it represents the minimum size of a cluster for the determination of local outliers), and I chose 5% of the total number of patients as the maximum value, considering that it represents the size of the larger cluster that can be regarded as a cluster of outliers. I assigned an LOF for each patient, for each value of `minPts` included in this interval. For each patient, the maximum LOF was assigned as definitive value. The calculation of LOF was performed by the function `lof()` of the package `dbscan`. The distribution of the LOF was used to test the hypothesis of being an outlier for each of the three added cases by one-sided testing with a cut-off for significance of 0.05.

Correlations

Correlation tables between variables were computed using the Spearman coefficient. Only significant correlations were reported (two-sided test, cut-off for significance of 0.05). I employed the package `corplot`.

Comparisons

Subjects were divided into two groups by various criteria (males vs females, outliers vs non-outliers, etc), then the two groups were compared using the Fisher test for binary variables and the T-test for non-binary ones. P-values were corrected for multiple comparisons using the Benjamini-Hochberg method, implemented by the function `p.adjust` of the package `stats`.

Supervised classification

I trained both a Naive Bayes and a Logistic regression model to recognise individuals who are mostly housebound to very severe (`severity_n` above 4). For both models, I estimated mean sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy as a function of the threshold of the predicted probability used for classification. I used the same approach to test logistic regression and Naive Bayes to predict patients who deteriorate. I then applied the two logistic models to the three added patients.

Unsupervised classification and PCA

To search for clusters in an unbiased way, I used the `pam()` function from the `cluster` package. Also, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed using the `princomp()` function from the `stats` package, and the principal planes and the distribution of variance across the components were visualised using both a custom script and the `biplot()` function from the same package.

Results

Bimodal analysis of age at onset

The bimodal fit based on two gamma densities for the age at onset was significant only for males (Figure 1), according to the two-sided Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The lognormal fit gave a similar result, but the fit is less significant (see repository files). The normal fit was significant for males, but with a slightly higher p-value.

Figure 1. Gamma bimodal fit of age at first symptoms, performed by maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) by the function `mixfit()` of the R package `mixR`. The two-sided Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to test the null: the distribution comes from the fitted density.

The parameters of the two gamma densities for females, males, and both sexes are reported in Table 2. For the analogous results of the lognormal and normal distributions, see the files in the repository. Remember that only for males, the bimodal density significantly fits the data.

Group	Proportion	Mean	SD
Younger Females	0.53	26.44	12.6
Older Females	0.47	41.28	8.26
Younger Males	0.62	26.71	12.77
Older Males	0.38	42.75	8.15
Younger Both sexes	0.54	26.44	12.61
Older Both sexes	0.46	41.43	8.29

Table 2. Parameters of the two gamma densities whose combination fits the distribution of age at first symptoms. Stratification by sex.

Local outlier factor and PCA

The distribution of the Local Outlier Factor (LOF) is shown in Figure 2, where the LOF of patient PT1 (folder Supplementary Cases) is also indicated by a red line. We see that this patient is an outlier because it displays an LOF that is greater than the 0.95 quantile of the distribution. This patient is a 46 yo male who got sick in his twenties and who has been housebound for most of the disease course. He also has low myalgia and high dizziness. According to this analysis, either he has another disease, or he is a case of monogenic ME/CFS (see discussion section). For the analogous plots of the other two added patients, see the file section.

Figure 2. Distribution of Local Outlier Factor for the about 9,600 patients included in this analysis. The vertical line indicates the LOF of PT1 (one of the three added patients), a male subject who developed ME/CFS at 20 and who has been mostly housebound ever since. The p-value refers to the null: PT1 belongs to the population of ME/CFS patients.

For each added patient, the script plots the position on the three principal planes after computing loadings (available in the file section). In Figure 3, the results of the PCA, with the position of PT1 on the principal planes.

Figure 3. Results of PCA, represented twice. Left: positions of all the patients on the three principal planes, including PT1 in red, and also representation of the space PC1-PC2-PC3. Right: same as before, with the projections of the axes of the space of the data on the principal planes (in red), the projection of PT1 (in red), and the distribution of the variance across the principal components. Loadings are available among the files of this repository. Since the variance is spread across most of the principal components, this analysis has little significance.

Correlations and comparisons

The correlation table is reported in Figure 4. Note that the two multi-level variables `course_n` and `trigger_n` were translated into binary variables, one for each level. Only significant correlations are reported (significance level: 0.05). We note that fatigue, PEM, pain, dizziness, sleep problems, sensitivity, and fibromyalgia positively correlate with deterioration. We note that females tend to correlate with all the comorbidities and most symptoms, except fatigue.

Figure 4. Correlation table. Gender is 2 for females and 1 for males. AIS_n: accident/injury/surgery.

When comparing males and females, the variables that are significantly different after correction for multiple comparisons are in Table 3. Females have more comorbidities overall, they are older, with a longer disease duration, have more PEM, and are less likely to be stable. Females are also less likely to begin the disease after an infection, but more likely to indicate vaccination as the triggering event (perhaps because of papillomavirus vaccination?). Females have a smaller LOF than males. Despite these differences, females are not more severe and more fatigued than males. The prevalence of endometriosis among women with ME/CFS does not appear to be higher than what has been documented in the general population (Moradi Y et al. 2021)

Variable	Females (n=8198)	Males (n=1398)	P-value	Adjusted P-value
endometriosis_n	8.94%	0%	8.37e-53	1.42e-51
sensitivity_n	3.66 (1.1)	3.19 (1.24)	5.02e-39	5.69e-38
fibromyalgia_n	33.9%	19.6%	5.14e-28	4.37e-27
migraine_n	31.5%	18.53%	2.77e-24	1.88e-23
pregnancy_n	2.82%	0.07%	7.29e-15	4.13e-14
musclemjointpain_n	3.62 (1.16)	3.34 (1.31)	2.07e-13	1.01e-12

Variable	Females (n=8198)	Males (n=1398)	P-value	Adjusted P-value
Hashimotosthyroiditis_n	9.56%	4.22%	2.37e-12	1.01e-11
irritablebowelsyndrome_n	43.1%	33.26%	3.91e-12	1.48e-11
interstitialcystitis_n	3.5%	0.93%	9.57e-09	3.25e-08
dizziness_n	3.02 (1.25)	2.81 (1.26)	2.87e-08	8.87e-08
siccasyndrome_n	5.57%	2.58%	5.29e-07	1.50e-06
age	47.9 (13.43)	45.99 (14.98)	8.10e-06	2.12e-05
duration	15.49 (10.99)	14.15 (10.64)	1.46e-05	3.55e-05
allergies_n	38.55%	32.55%	1.69e-05	3.83e-05
lof	1.08 (0.12)	1.1 (0.14)	5.99e-05	1.27e-04
multiplechemicalsensitivities_n	14.2%	10.44%	1.23e-04	2.46e-04
infection_n	49.23%	54.58%	2.36e-04	4.46e-04
vaccine_n	4.44%	2.43%	2.71e-04	4.85e-04
sleepproblems_n	3.86 (1.09)	3.75 (1.15)	6.97e-04	1.18e-03
trauma_n	5.61%	3.51%	7.72e-04	1.25e-03
pem_n	4.62 (0.72)	4.54 (0.81)	1.60e-03	2.47e-03
asthma_n	16.59%	13.45%	3.15e-03	4.66e-03
no_trigger_n	13.88%	16.88%	3.80e-03	5.17e-03
other_n	13.88%	16.88%	3.80e-03	5.17e-03
AIS_n	4.7%	3.22%	1.18e-02	1.54e-02
stable_n	23.32%	25.89%	3.79e-02	4.77e-02

Table 3. Comparison between females and males. Only significant differences were included, after BH correction for multiple comparisons (see file section for the complete table). Note that pregnancy_n indicates as trigger both pregnancy and birth.

When we assign males to two groups based on the probability of belonging to the two densities in Table 1, we obtain the results collected in Table 4. We see that those who got sick at a younger age have a longer disease duration despite being younger. They are more severe and more isolated in the space of the variables, according to their mean LOF. They have more sensitivity, dizziness, and sleep problems, but less pain.

Variable	M_comp_1 (n=769)	M_comp_2 (n=629)	P-value	Adjusted P-value
age_ill	22.13 (8.84)	43.71 (6.57)	0.00e+00	0.00e+00
comp.prob.1	0.88 (0.16)	0.30 (0.07)	0.00e+00	0.00e+00
comp.prob.2	0.12 (0.16)	0.70 (0.07)	0.00e+00	0.00e+00
age	38.05 (14.27)	55.69 (8.89)	1.79e-137	1.52e-136
duration	15.92 (12.13)	11.98 (7.97)	5.72e-13	3.89e-12
severity_n	3.99 (0.87)	3.77 (0.81)	8.66e-07	4.91e-06
lof	1.11 (0.16)	1.09 (0.10)	1.20e-03	5.83e-03
sensitivity_n	3.27 (1.25)	3.08 (1.22)	4.89e-03	2.08e-02
dizziness_n	2.89 (1.28)	2.72 (1.22)	8.54e-03	2.90e-02
sleepproblems_n	3.82 (1.13)	3.66 (1.17)	7.84e-03	2.90e-02
muscleorjointpain_n	3.26 (1.35)	3.44 (1.27)	1.09e-02	3.37e-02

Table 4. Comparison between males more likely to belong to those who developed the disease at a young age, versus the others, according to the results in Figure 1 and Table 2. Variable comp.prob.1 indicates the probability of being

part of the density with a lower mean. Analogously for comp.prob.2.

In Table 5, I collected the results of the comparison between the subjects with a severity from 4 (mostly housebound) to 6 (very severe), and all the others. The first group displays worse fatigue, dizziness, PEM, sensitivity, pain, fibromyalgia, sleep problems, migraine, allergies, asthma, interstitial cystitis, endometriosis, and sicca syndrome. The more severe group is more likely to be deteriorating, is younger, includes more females, developed the disease at a younger age, and has a longer disease duration. Also, patients with a more severe ME/CFS are more likely to have relatives with ME/CFS. Infection is more likely to be the initial trigger in housebound patients than in the less severe ones.

Variable	Housebound (n=7093)	notHousebound (n=2503)	P-value	Adjusted P-value
severity_n	4.29 (0.53)	2.86 (0.37)	0.00e+00	0.00e+00
fatigue_n	4.71 (0.59)	3.94 (0.85)	8.48e-313	1.44e-311
deteriorating_n	55.67 %	17.66 %	9.21e-254	1.04e-252
dizziness_n	3.18 (1.24)	2.42 (1.10)	4.73e-170	4.02e-169
pem_n	4.75 (0.61)	4.20 (0.90)	9.15e-155	6.22e-154
sensitivity_n	3.77 (1.07)	3.07 (1.15)	1.29e-144	7.31e-144
improving_n	3.10 %	18.58 %	2.75e-126	1.34e-125
muscleorjointpain_n	3.73 (1.16)	3.15 (1.16)	2.72e-97	1.16e-96
sleepproblems_n	3.98 (1.04)	3.46 (1.16)	1.68e-84	6.35e-84
stable_n	19.70 %	35.04 %	1.60e-51	5.44e-51
fibromyalgia_n	34.34 %	24.65 %	1.11e-19	3.43e-19
irritablebowelsyndrome_n	43.96 %	35.16 %	1.18e-14	3.34e-14
migraine_n	31.58 %	24.01 %	5.39e-13	1.41e-12
fluctuating_n	21.53 %	28.73 %	5.84e-13	1.42e-12
multiplechemicalsensitivities_n	15.10 %	9.55 %	7.82e-13	1.77e-12
age_ill	31.88 (12.90)	33.58 (12.52)	8.18e-09	1.74e-08
lof	1.08 (0.12)	1.10 (0.12)	2.14e-07	4.28e-07
allergies_n	38.80 %	34.48 %	1.24e-04	2.34e-04
duration	15.54 (11.11)	14.61 (10.43)	1.64e-04	2.93e-04
relatives_n	15.56 %	13.14 %	3.33e-03	5.66e-03
asthma_n	16.73 %	14.42 %	6.57e-03	1.06e-02
no_trigger_n	13.76 %	15.90 %	9.61e-03	1.42e-02
other_n	13.76 %	15.90 %	9.61e-03	1.42e-02
trauma_n	4.96 %	6.27 %	1.28e-02	1.81e-02
gender_n	85.96 %	83.94 %	1.47e-02	2.00e-02
age	47.42 (13.61)	48.19 (13.89)	1.75e-02	2.29e-02
infection_n	50.71 %	48.02 %	2.14e-02	2.69e-02
interstitialcystitis_n	3.37 %	2.44 %	2.29e-02	2.78e-02
endometriosis_n	7.99 %	6.63 %	2.86e-02	3.35e-02
siccasyndrome_n	5.43 %	4.31 %	3.08e-02	3.49e-02
AIS_n	4.74 %	3.76 %	4.30e-02	4.72e-02

Table 5. Comparison between individuals who are housebound or worse, and the others. AIS_n: accident/injury/surgery.

ME/CFS patients with affected relatives (Table 6) have a longer disease duration and developed the disease earlier. They have more MCS, fibromyalgia, allergies, migraine, sensitivity, and dizziness. They are more severe and are more isolated in the variable space (higher LOF). They are older.

Variables	aff_relatives (1433)	no_aff_relatives (8163)	p.val	p.adjust
relatives_n	100 %	0 %	0.00e+00	0.00e+00
duration	18.2 (12.36)	14.78 (10.6)	2.39e-22	4.06e-21
age_ill	30.29 (13.73)	32.68 (12.63)	8.42e-10	9.54e-09
lof	1.11 (0.14)	1.08 (0.12)	1.36e-09	1.16e-08
multiplechemicalsensitivities_n	18.63 %	12.78 %	9.79e-09	6.66e-08
fibromyalgia_n	36.64 %	30.97 %	2.85e-05	1.62e-04
allergies_n	41.87 %	36.93 %	4.34e-04	2.11e-03
migraine_n	33.43 %	28.94 %	7.00e-04	2.97e-03
sensitivity_n	3.68 (1.12)	3.57 (1.13)	9.57e-04	3.62e-03
severity_n	3.98 (0.82)	3.91 (0.79)	2.74e-03	9.32e-03
dizziness_n	3.07 (1.23)	2.97 (1.25)	6.15e-03	1.90e-02
age	48.49 (14.48)	47.47 (13.54)	1.31e-02	3.71e-02

Table 6. Comparison between patients with and patients without affected relatives.

In Table 7, I compared outliers (LOF above the 0.9 quantile) with the others. Outliers display an increased prevalence of deterioration over time, are less likely to develop the disease after an infection, and have their first symptoms at a younger age. They have less fatigue and less PEM. Variances are larger among outliers, suggesting that they do not define a homogeneous group.

Variable	common (n=9116)	outliers (n=480)	P-value	Adjusted P-value
lof	1.06 (0.06)	1.49 (0.24)	1.43e-151	4.86e-150
duration	14.64 (9.81)	27.76 (20.1)	1.15e-38	1.96e-37
age	47.15 (13.14)	56.51 (19.53)	5.84e-23	6.62e-22
pem_n	4.64 (0.64)	4.00 (1.61)	1.07e-16	9.10e-16
fatigue_n	4.53 (0.69)	4.14 (1.39)	1.30e-09	8.84e-09
muscleorjointpain_n	3.60 (1.17)	3.24 (1.48)	2.34e-07	1.33e-06
multiplechemicalsensitivities_n	13.23 %	21.67 %	7.68e-07	3.73e-06
relatives_n	14.56 %	22.08 %	1.78e-05	7.56e-05
age_ill	32.52 (11.98)	28.74 (23.4)	4.96e-04	1.87e-03
interstitialcystitis_n	2.97 %	6.04 %	6.31e-04	1.95e-03
stable_n	24.03 %	17.29 %	6.20e-04	1.95e-03
deteriorating_n	45.39 %	52.71 %	1.90e-03	5.38e-03
infection_n	50.35 %	43.54 %	3.68e-03	9.62e-03
sleepproblems_n	3.85 (1.08)	3.70 (1.36)	1.91e-02	4.06e-02
no_trigger_n	14.12 %	18.12 %	1.90e-02	4.06e-02
other_n	14.12 %	18.12 %	1.90e-02	4.06e-02

Table 6. Comparison between patients with LOF above the 0.95 quantile (outliers) and the others (common).

Machine Learning

Supervised classification of severity

The performances of the logistic and Naive Bayes models in predicting the severity of the patients from the other variables are documented in Figures 5 and 6, respectively. The logistic classifier shows a better profile: using as a cut-off a predicted probability of 0.75, it reaches a sensitivity and a specificity of 0.75.

Figure 5. Performances of a logistic regression, with severity as the outcome variable (its value is one for patients who are housebound or worse, zero otherwise). For each value of the cut-off of the predicted probability used to classify the subject, resampling was randomly performed 40 times; then, mean sensitivity and specificity were calculated and plotted. Left: sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, type I error (ERI), and type II error (ERII) are plotted as a function of the predictive-probability cut-off. Right: Sensitivity is plotted as a function of false positive rate.

Figure 6. Performances of a Naive Bayes supervised classification, with severity as exit variable. For details, see the caption of Figure 5.

The significant coefficients of the logistic regression applied to all the available data are reported in Table 8. We see that the significant positive predictors of severity are fatigue, dizziness, PEM, sensitivity, sleep problems, and the presence of relatives with the same disease. On the other hand, a course of the disease that is stable, fluctuating or improving negatively regresses with severity. Also, starting the illness after a traumatic life event predicts a less severe profile.

Variable	Estimate	SE	Z	p-value	Sign.
(Intercept)	-5.6934	0.3066	-18.569	< 2e-16	***
fatigue_n	0.9764	0.0420	23.259	< 2e-16	***
dizziness_n	0.2307	0.0256	9.005	< 2e-16	***
sensitivity_n	0.2238	0.0278	8.045	8.63e-16	***
pem_n	0.3224	0.0391	8.236	< 2e-16	***
stable_n	-1.1637	0.0750	-15.527	< 2e-16	***
fluctuating_n	-1.1767	0.0744	-15.812	< 2e-16	***
improving_n	-2.0894	0.1103	-18.936	< 2e-16	***
trauma_n	-0.3639	0.1335	-2.727	6.39e-03	**
sleepproblems_n	0.0663	0.0271	2.447	1.44e-02	*
relatives_n	0.1975	0.0825	2.394	1.67e-02	*

Table 8. Significant coefficients of the logistic regression between a binary variable for severity (1 if house-bound or worse, 0 otherwise) and all the available variables.

Supervised classification of outliers

I also trained two models (logistic regression and Naive Bayes) to predict LOF. Their performances in predicting outliers (LOF>0.95th percentile) are reported in Figures 7 and 8, respectively. Naive-Bayes outperforms logistic regression in this case.

Figure 7. Performances of a logistic regression, with LOF as the outcome variable (its value is one for LOF above the 95th percentile, zero otherwise). For each value of the cut-off of the predicted probability used to classify the subject, resampling was randomly performed 40 times. Next, the mean sensitivity and specificity were calculated and plotted. Left: sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, type I error (ERI), and type II error (ERII) are plotted as a function of the predictive-probability cut-off. Right: Sensitivity is plotted as a function of false positive rate.

Figure 8. Performances of a Naive Bayes model, with LOF as the outcome variable (its value is one for LOF above the 95th percentile, zero otherwise). See Figure 7 for details.

The significant coefficients of the logistic regression are indicated below (Table 9). We see that fatigue, sensitivity, pain, and PEM predict non-outlier status. A younger age at first symptoms predicts outlier status, as well as severity. Fluctuations or stability in disease course predict non-outlier status.

Variable	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p-value	Sig
fatigue_n	-0.375022	0.068515	-5.474	4.41e-08	***
muscleorjointpain_n	-0.239960	0.050479	-4.754	2.00e-06	***
sensitivity_n	0.107491	0.052813	2.035	0.04182	*
pem_n	-0.735165	0.055192	-13.320	<2e-16	***
interstitialcystitis_n	0.503695	0.232031	2.171	0.02995	*
severity_n	0.463162	0.079351	5.837	5.32e-09	***
age_ill	-0.074715	0.004436	-16.842	<2e-16	***
age	0.093339	0.004700	19.861	<2e-16	***
stable_n	-0.428085	0.154072	-2.778	0.00546	**
fluctuating_n	-0.297612	0.140359	-2.120	0.03398	*

Table 9. Significant coefficients that predict outlier status (1 for outlier, 0 for non-outlier) using a logistic regression.

Supervised classification of deterioration

I trained the logistic and the Naive Bayes models to recognise subjects who deteriorate over time, using as an outcome a binary variable whose value is one when course_n is 5 (fluctuating initially, then mostly deterioration) or 7 (mainly deterioration), zero otherwise. The performances of the two models, evaluated by resampling, are described by Figures 9 and 10.

Figure 9. Performances of a logistic regression, using as an outcome a binary variable whose value is one when course_n is 5 (fluctuating initially, then mostly deterioration) or 7 (mainly deterioration), zero otherwise. For each value of the cut-off of the predicted probability used to classify the subject, resampling was randomly performed 40 times. Next, the mean sensitivity and specificity were calculated and plotted. Left: sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, type I error (ERI), and type II error (ERII) are plotted as a function of the predictive-probability cut-off. Right: Sensitivity is plotted as a function of false positive rate.

Figure 8. Performances of a Naive Bayes model. See Figure 9 for details.

The significant coefficients of the logistic regression are in Table 10. Positive predictors of deterioration are pain, fatigue, dizziness, sleep problems, PEM, Fibromyalgia, IBS, asthma, and disease severity. Having relatives with ME is a protective factor against deterioration, as well as a younger age at first symptoms.

Variable	Estimate	p-value	Significance
Intercept	-9.27	<2e-16	***
Relatives with ME	-0.19	0.004	**
Fatigue	0.29	6.62e-14	***
Muscle or Joint Pain	0.08	0.00021	***
Dizziness	0.07	0.00032	***
Sleep Problems	0.11	4.37e-06	***
Post-Exertional Malaise (PEM)	0.17	7.04e-06	***
Fibromyalgia	0.21	0.00011	***
Irritable Bowel Syndrome	0.17	0.00062	***
Allergies	-0.16	0.0016	**
Asthma	0.14	0.027	*
Disease Severity	1.03	<2e-16	***
Age at Illness Onset	-0.005	0.041	*
Age	0.009	0.00020	***
LOF	1.37	2.84e-09	***

Table 10. Significant coefficients that predict deterioration status (1 for deterioration, 0 otherwise) using a logistic regression.

Prediction for three patients

I applied three of the classifiers discussed above to the supplementary patients included in folder Supplementary Cases (Table 11). The cut-off for the three classifiers employed is as follows: 75% for the housebound status predictor (logistic, Figure 5), 5% for the outlier classifier (NB model of Figure 8), and 50% for the classifier of deterioration (logistic regression of Figure 9)

Patient	Outlier	Prediction	Housebound	Prediction	Deteriorating	Prediction
PT1	Yes	Yes (10%)	Yes	Yes (87%)	No	No (45%)
PT2	No	No (4%)	Yes	Yes (83%)	Yes	Yes (65%)
PT3	No	No (1%)	Yes	No (40%)	No	Yes (58%)

Table 11. Predictions about outlier status, deterioration, and severity for the three patients included in folder Supplementary Cases.

Unsupervised clustering

Partitioning (clustering) of the data into k clusters around medoids, for k from 2 to 7, failed at finding separated clusters (see folder Unsupervised for details). Principal Component Analysis provides little contribution to this analysis because 80% of the total variance is distributed across 16 principal components (Figure 3).

Discussion

Monogenic forms of common idiopathic diseases have been documented in Alzheimer's Disease (AD) (Barber RC 2012), Parkinson's Disease (PD) (Girija MS et Kishore A 2025), and Frontotemporal Dementia (FTD) (Barbier M et al. 2018). Using PD as a paradigmatic case, we observe that despite a substantial overlap in clinical presentation, monogenic forms often display atypical symptoms (due to the specific gene affected) and an early onset. Also, the study of monogenic cases has offered important insights into the mechanisms of the idiopathic form (Girija MS et Kishore A 2025).

Myalgic Encephalomyelitis/Chronic Fatigue Syndrome (ME/CFS) is a complex disease defined by persistent fatigue, exacerbation of post-exertional symptoms, cognitive impairment and orthostatic intolerance (Chu L et al. 2019), with a prevalence of 0.009 (Lim EJ et al. 2020). A recent GWAS meta-analysis on 21,560 ME/CFS patients including data from DecodeME, UK Biobank, and Million Veteran Program, revealed a possible involvement of the glutamatergic synapses (Maccallini 2025) (Maccallini 2026). On the other hand, only a few attempts have been published to document Mendelian ME/CFS (MME) by next-generation sequencing (NGS), tagging genes NOS3 (McGarrity S. et al. 2024) and AKRIC1/AKRIC2 (Oakley J et al. 2023). With the planned whole-genome sequencing (WGS) study of more than 18k patients announced by the DecodeME group, this landscape is likely to change drastically, with a sharp increase in well-documented MME cases.

Soon, clinicians will face the challenge of selecting subjects with ME/CFS to send for WGS, along with their family members. We do not yet know what peculiar features to look for in this population. Here, I propose an unsupervised selector based on the Local Outlier Factor (LOF) algorithm (Breunig MM, 2000) applied to the raw data from the EMEA Pan-European ME Patient Survey (Angelsen A et Schei T, 2024).

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